

Analysis Of Labour Use Among Rural Maize Farmers in Ogbomosho South Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study analyzed labour use among rural maize farmers in Ogbomosho South Local Government Area of Oyo state, Nigeria. A total number of (120) respondent were selected for the study using multi-stage sampling technique. Well-structured interview schedule was used for data collection from the respondents with the aid of multi-stage techniques. Statistics such as frequency table, percentage and mean was used to analyze the research work while Chi-square was used as inferential tool used to analyze the data of the study. The results showed that majority (75.8%) of the respondents were male. Majority (81.7%) were married with the mean age of 46 years. The mean household size was 6. The mean year spent in school was 6 years, majority (75.8%) of the respondents belong to social association. Hired labour had the highest Weighted Mean Score (WMS) of 1.84 and personal labour (WMS=1.78) were the major labour utilized while Low labour cost had the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 1.73 and ranked 1st, as the major effect of labour used. Seasonal migration of labour had the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 1.76 and high cost of labour (WMS=1.75) were the major constraints to the usage of labour. Chi-square analysis shows a significant relationship between some selected socioeconomic characteristics such as sex ($\chi=32.033$, $p=0.000$), marital status ($\chi=209.533$, $p=0.000$), religion ($\chi=52.650$, $p=0.000$), primary occupation ($\chi=46.333$, $p=0.000$) and level of income ($\chi=28.800$, $p=0.000$) and labour usage.

It was concluded that most of the respondents were still in their active age. Majority of the respondents were male, married. Majority utilized hired labour while labour cost was seen by the respondents as the major factor influencing the choice of labour usage in the study area and then recommended that Agricultural credit schemes should be organized by the government for farmers in order for them to be able to afford the services of hired labour.

1. INTRODUCTION: -

Agricultural sector in Nigeria is one of the leading sectors in terms of its contributions to income, employment, foreign exchange earnings and domestic food supply (Omojimito, 2012). Agriculture continues to be a strategic sector in the development of most low-income nations. It employs about 40% of the active labour force globally. In Nigeria, Agriculture contributes more than 30% of the total annual GDP, employs about 70% of the labour force, accounts for over 70% of the non-oil exports and, perhaps most important, provided over 80% of the food needs of the country (Adegboye, 2004; Ebojei *et al.*, 2012). This makes agriculture as one of the most important sectors of the Nigerian economy.

Maize (*Zea mays*) is a member of the grass family (gramineae). It originated from South and Central America. It was introduced to West Africa by the Portuguese in the 10th century. Maize is one of the important grains in Nigeria, not

only on the basis of the number of farmers that engaged in its cultivation, but also in its economic value. Maize is a major important cereal crop being cultivated in the rainforest and the derived savannah zones of Nigeria. Maize has been in the diet of Nigerians for centuries. It started as a subsistence crop and has gradually become more important crop. Maize has now risen to a commercial crop on which many agro-based industries depend on as raw materials (Iken and Amusa, 2004). Maize is highly yielding, easy to process, readily digested and cost less than other cereals. It is also a versatile crop, allowing it to grow across a range of agroecological zones (IITA, 2001). It is an important source of carbohydrate and if eaten in the immature state, provides useful quantities of Vitamin A and C. Maize thrives best in a warm climate and is now grown in most of the countries that have suitable climatic conditions.

Maize is one of the most important staple food crops in Nigeria. It is the second most common cereal food crop after rice. Maize is a very important food crop for human beings and for livestock. It provides energy, vitamins and negligible amount of protein. Output of maize has continued to increase in Nigeria. For example, in 1986, about 1336 metric tonnes of maize was produced in Nigeria, while in 2003 about 7019 metric tonnes was produced (CBN, 2003). The livestock industry consumes more than half of the total annual maize production. Maize originated in Central and South America and was introduced into Africa by Portuguese in the 16th century. A report had it was introduced to Europe in 1492 from central and southern America by Christopher Columbus and latter spread to Africa by the Dutch in southern Africa (Okoruwa, 2006). Maize is a major and important cereals being cultivated in the Rainforest and derived savannah zone of Nigeria. It is also one of the popular cereals in Nigeria; it serves as the main staple food for millions of Nigerians.

Labour plays important economic and social roles in any economy. In Nigeria, farm labour is a major source of employment opportunity for the rural labour force and technological change is one of the major forces leading to change in employment, output and functional income distribution. It is one of the key factors of production as well as a source of livelihood to billions of people worldwide (Schneider, 2005). Nigeria's agricultural production is highly labour intensive. Over 90% of non-mechanized production systems depend on human labour, and for mechanized production systems, between 50 and 60% of the tasks depend on human labour (Olayide, 2002). Family labour constitutes over 76% of farm labour and human labour is about the only form of farm labour available to farmers and farmers contribute over 80% of total domestic agricultural output, it therefore means that, human labour accounts for domestic food supplies in Nigeria in general (Shaib et al., 1997). Therefore, the hope to continue to supply the food need of the ever-growing population anchors very auspiciously on human labour productivity. In Nigeria, labour is a major constraint in food crop production (Gocowski and Oduwole, 2003). The availability of labour has been found to have impact on planting precision, better weed control, timely harvesting and crop processing (Oluyole et al., 2007). Several problems are associated with agriculture and over the years agricultural production has drastically reduced (Ogundari and Ojo, 2006). The importance of food crop and agricultural production to the world requires the efforts of farm labour suppliers. The efforts, as observed from some researchers were apparently hindered due to some factors such as Migration, Wage rate, farm income, age composition, barrier to adoption of technology and effect of diseases on farm labour suppliers.

The ability of the farmer to perform his role in agricultural development according to Ogunsumi *et al.* (2005), has been on the decline in the last three decades. One of the reasons identified as the cause of the declining performance of the sector is inefficient allocation of available farm resources; Land, labour, seed, and fertilizer, these managerial resources are inefficiently allocated thereby leading to decrease in productivity and reduced agricultural output. The trends in yields have been very disappointing and characterized by very unstable and mostly negative growth. For example, between 1998/2000 and 2001/2003, negative growth rate in yield was observed for maize, sorghum, rice, cassava, yam and rubber. It has also placed a serious stress on the marketing systems (Ojo and Imoudu, 2000). Also Nigeria produced 7.5 million metric tons in 2008 and decline to 7 million metric tons in 2012, FAO (2014). The

growth in output in the face of declining yields suggests that the bulk of the production increase is accounted for by expansion in cultivated area.

Labour supply from the family level has been dwindling considerably over the past years due to a number of factors, some of which are related. The achievement of the international labour organization in child labour prevention coupled with the increasing awareness of the importance of education even in the rural areas has increased the proportion of children in schools hence reducing time available to work on the farm (Diallo et al., 2013). Hunger and poor nutrition with their resultant ill-health and sometimes deaths, have also taken its toll on available labour from farming families. Rural-urban migration and the more attractive off-farm labour requirement have left mainly the aged and less mobile farmers to work on the farms (Oluyole et al., 2013). Amsalu et al. (2013) opined that shortage of farm labour at peak seasons may be a reason for households to hire farm labour. Hired labour is not only relevant where family labour is inadequate. The much-desired transition from small-scale farming to commercial level production by expansion of production resources definitely requires outsourcing for additional labour. According to Blanc et al. (2008) the proportion of hired labour in total farm labour use in many developing countries has continued to increase over time. There is a possibility therefore that agricultural productivity in Nigeria may be limited as a result of lack of able body and energetic labour thus affecting food security. Therefore, this study provided answers to the following questions. Therefore, the main objective of this research is to examine the analysis of labour use among rural maize farmers in Ogbomoso South local government, Oyo State. Specifically, the study described the socio economic characteristics of rural maize farmers in the study area: identified the different labour sources available in the study area, examined the factors influencing the choice of farm labour and investigated the constraints to labour use in the study area.

2. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS: -

H₀₁: there is no significant relationship between socio economic characteristics of the respondents and the use of labour by the maize farmers.

3. METHODOLOGY: -

The population of the study comprised of all maize farmers in the study area. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 120 respondents for this study. Data for this study was collected through the use of a well-structured interview schedule. Both the dependent and independent variables were measured in this study. The dependent variable of this study is the analysis of labour use among maize farmers which was measured on a 3-scale of always, sometimes and never. Both descriptive and inferential tools were used for this study. Descriptive statistics that was used includes frequency, percentages and standard deviation while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used as the inferential tool to test the hypothesis of the study.

4. RESULT AND DSCUSSION: -

Socio-economic Characteristics

Table 1 shows that majority (75.8%) of the respondents were male while 24.2% were females, 37.5% of the respondents were between the age of 51-60 years, 29% of the respondent were above sixty years of age, 23.3% were

between 41-50 years while 10.8% of respondents were less than equal to 40 years of age. The mean age of respondents was 42 years which suggests that the respondents are still within the productive age bracket and would possess the vigor required for agricultural production. Household size shows that 47.5% were less than equal to 5 members, 35.8% were between 6-10 while 16.6% were above 10 members. The mean household size was 6. A high percentage of the respondents (81.7%) were married, 13.3% were widowed, 4.2% were separated while 0.8% were divorced. The results implies that majority are married and this is assumed to create some stability in the home and make family labour available for their agricultural production. The mean year spent in school was 6 years. Majority (95.0%) indicated farming as their primary occupation, only few were traders with 5.0%. This implies that agricultural activities and trading was the major occupation of the respondents in the study area. Majority (75.8%) of the respondents belong to an association while 24.2% do not belong to any association. Also, 58.3% of the respondents cultivated between 2-3ha 27.5% cultivated 1ha and below while 14.1% of the respondents cultivated above 3ha. The mean farm size was 2ha. This implies that majority of the respondents still cultivate a small scale, and this could be as a result of inadequate access to capital, farm input and lack of labour usage on their maize farm.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to socio-economic characteristics

Socio economic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	91	75.8
Female	29	24.2
Age		
≤ 40	13	10.8
41 – 50	28	23.3
51 – 60	45	37.5
Marital status		
Married	98	81.7
Divorced	1	0.8
Widowed	16	13.3
Separated	5	4.2
Educational level		
No formal education	24	20.0
Primary school completed	38	31.7
Primary school uncompleted	33	27.5
Secondary school completed	15	12.5
Secondary school uncompleted	6	5.0
Tertiary school completed	3	2.5
Tertiary school uncompleted	1	0.8
Year spent in school		
≤ 5	57	47.5
6 – 10	43	35.8
Above 10	20	16.6
Religion		
Islam	67	55.8

Christian	49	40.8
Traditional worshipper	4	3.3
Primary occupation		
Farming	53	44.2
Trading	22	18.3
Civil service	4	3.3
Artisan	41	34.2
Secondary occupation		
Farming	114	95.0
Trading	6	5.0
Civil service	-	-
Artisan	-	-
Membership of Association		
Yes	91	75.8
No	29	24.2
Name of Association		
Farmer's association	35	29.2
Community association	22	18.3
Cooperative society	33	27.5
None	30	25.0
Years of membership		
≤ 10	65	54.2
11 – 20	39	32.5
Above 20	16	13.2
Farm size		
≤ 1	33	27.5
2 – 3	69	58.3
Above 3	17	14.1
Maize output before the use of hired labour		
≤ 3000	44	36.5
3001 – 5000	51	42.5
Above 5000	25	20.6
Maize output after the use of hired labour		
≤ 3000	38	31.6
3001 – 5000	43	35.8
Above 5000	39	32.4
Total	120	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2022

Type of labour source utilized

Result in Table 2 revealed the distribution of respondent according to type of labour source utilized. The result shows that hired labour had the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 1.84 and ranked 1st, this is followed by personal labour with weighted mean score and family labour with a joint weighted mean score of 0.93. Others are borrowed labour (WMS=0.32), casual labour (WMS=0.28) while share cropping was ranked 6th with weighted mean score of 0.16. This implies that hired labour was mostly utilized labour identified by the respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to type of labour source utilized

Type of labour source	Always	Sometimes	Never	WMS	Rank
Family labour	14(11.7)	84(70.0)	22(18.3)	0.93	3 rd
Hired labour	103(85.8)	15(12.5)	2(1.7)	1.84	1 st
Personal labour	56(46.7)	60(50.0)	4(3.3)	1.43	2 nd
Borrowed labour	7(5.8)	24(20.0)	89(74.2)	0.32	4 th
Exchange labour	3(2.5)	10(8.3)	107(89.2)	0.13	7 th
Casual labour	3(2.5)	28(23.3)	89(74.2)	0.28	5 th
Share labour	5(4.2)	9(7.5)	106(88.3)	0.16	6 th

Source: Field survey, 2022

Factors that influenced the choice of farm labour

The result in Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents according to the factor that influenced the choice of farm labour. The result revealed that low labour cost had the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 1.73 and ranked 1st, followed by high income of farmers with weighted mean score of 1.72 and ranked 2nd, while small house size was ranked 3rd (WMS=1.42). Others are in the following order: low income of farmers (WMS=1.67), low educational level of farmers (WMS=1.65), age of farmer (young) (WMS=1.64), far distance of farm (WMS=1.61), age of farmer (old) (WMS=1.57), high labour cost (WMS=1.54), large farm size (WMS=1.52), large household size (WMS=1.49), low farming experience (WMS=1.43), higher farming experience (WMS=1.42), high educational level of farmers (WMS=1.37), near distance of farm (WMS=1.30) while small farm size was ranked 16th with weighted mean score of 1.24. This implies that low labour cost was the major factor influencing the choice of farm labour in the study area.

Table 3: Distribution of respondents according to factors that influences the choice of farm labour

Factors	Major factor	Minor factor	Not a factor	WMS	Rank
Low educational level of farmer	83(69.2)	32(26.7)	5(4.2)	1.65	5 th

High educational level of farmer	61(50.8)	42(35.0)	17(14.2)	1.37	14 th
Age of farmer (old)	75(62.5)	38(31.7)	7(5.8)	1.57	8 th
Age of farmer (young)	90(75.0)	17(14.2)	13(10.8)	1.64	6 th
High labour cost	71(59.2)	43(35.8)	6(5.0)	1.54	9 th
Low labour cost	94(78.3)	20(16.7)	6(5.0)	1.73	1 st
Large farm size	68(56.7)	46(38.3)	6(5.0)	1.52	10 th
Small farm size	39(32.5)	71(59.2)	10(8.3)	1.24	16 th
Large household size	68(56.7)	43(35.8)	9(7.5)	1.49	11 th
Small household size	90(75.0)	24(20.0)	6(5.0)	1.70	3 rd
Higher farming experience	58(48.3)	54(45.0)	8(6.7)	1.42	13 th
Low farming experience	56(46.7)	60(50.0)	4(3.3)	1.43	12 th
Far distance of farm	77(64.2)	39(32.5)	4(3.3)	1.61	7 th
Near distance of farm	47(39.2)	62(51.7)	11(9.2)	1.30	15 th
Low income of farmer	83(69.2)	34(28.3)	3(2.5)	1.67	4 th
High income of farmer	92(76.7)	22(18.3)	6(5.0)	1.72	2 nd

Source: Field survey, 2022

Multiple Response Constraints faced by farmers in ensuring adequate supply of labour

Result in Table 4 shows the constraint faced by farmers in ensuring adequate supply of labour. The result shows that seasonal migration of labour had the highest weighted mean score (WMS) of 1.76 and ranked 1st, next to it is high cost of labour which was ranked 2nd with weighted mean score of 1.75 while theft by labourers / dishonesty from labourers was ranked 3rd with weighted mean score of 1.67. Others are in the following order: Long distance of farm location (WMS=1.56), unavailability / delay in accessing credit facilities (WMS=1.36) while presence of improved non-farm income was ranked 6th with weighted mean score of (1.13). The result implies that seasonal migration of labour was a major problem faced by farmers in ensuring adequate supply of labour in the study area.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents according to constraints faced by farmers in ensuring adequate supply of labour

Constraints	Major problem	Minor problem	Not a problem	wms	Rank
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Seasonal migration of labour	97(80.8)	17(14.2)	6(5.0)	1.76	1 st
High cost of labour	93(77.5)	24(20.0)	3(2.5)	1.75	2 nd
Theft by labourers/dishonesty from labourers	86(71.7)	28(23.3)	6(5.0)	1.67	3 rd
Presence of improved non-farm income	24(20.0)	87(72.5)	9(7.5)	1.13	6 th
Scarcity of youths in the study area	11(9.2)	35(29.2)	74(61.7)	0.48	7 th
Long distance of farm location	74(61.7)	39(32.5)	7(5.8)	1.56	4 th
Unavailability / delay in accessing Credit facilities	51(42.5)	61(50.8)	8(6.7)	1.36	5 th

Source: Field survey, 2022

WMS: weighted mean score

Test of Hypothesis

This section presents the result of the test of hypothesis that was formulated and tested in the study. The hypothesis of the study was stated in a null form and was tested to determine the relationship that exists between socio-economic characteristics of the respondent and labour usage.

The result of chi-square analysis shows a significant relationship between some selected socioeconomic characteristics such as sex ($x=32.033$, $p=0.000$), marital status ($x=209.533$, $p=0.000$), religion ($x=52.650$, $p=0.000$), primary occupation ($x=46.333$, $p=0.000$) and level of income ($x=28.800$, $p=0.000$) and labour usage.

H_A : The alternative hypothesis therefore states that there is a significant relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and labour use among maize farmers in the study area.

Table 5: Chi-square Analysis Showing Relationship between Selected Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents and Analysis of labour use among maize farmer

Variable	X ²	DF	P-value	Remarks	Decision
Sex	32.033	1	0.000	Significant	Rejected
Marital status	209.533	3	0.000	Significant	Rejected
Religion	52.650	2	0.000	Significant	Rejected
Primary occupation	46.333	3	0.000	Significant	Rejected
Level of income	155.167	9	0.000	Significant	Rejected

Computed Data, 2022

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION: -

It was concluded majority of the respondents utilized hired labour while labour cost was seen by the respondents as the major factor influencing the choice of labour usage in the study area and then recommends that agricultural credit schemes should be organized by the government for farmers in order for them to be able to afford the services of hired labour and also a deliberate rural development programme by government targeted at making rural communities conducive for people to stay especially the energetic youths is imperative for sustained supply of labour for the respondents.

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